

INVESTIGATING THE CORRELATION OF INCREASED TREND OF CORTICOSTEROIDS USE AND ASSOCIATED SKIN CHANGES IN ECZEMA PATIENTS

Raviha Ajmal Chaudhary¹, Zarmeen Ahsan², Kainat Falak³, Muhammad Huzaifa^{*}

^{1,2,3,*} Aesthetic and Cosmetology, Department of Emerging Health Professional Technologies, Allied Health Sciences, Superior University, Lahore, Pakistan

¹su91-baacm-f22-031@superior.edu.pk, ²su91-baacm-f22-029@superior.edu.pk, ³su91-baacm-f22-052@superior.edu.pk, ^{*}muhammadhuzaifa@superior.edu.pk

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20621721>

Keywords

Eczema, Topical Corticosteroids, Skin Changes, Steroid Misuse, Atrophy, Striae, Frequency, Duration, Dermatology

Article History

Received: 03 April 2026

Accepted: 15 May 2026

Published: 30 May 2026

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Muhammad Huzaifa

muhammadhuzaifa@superior.edu.pk

Abstract

Background: Eczema is a chronic inflammatory skin disorder seriously affecting patient's quality of life. The improper, longer and unsupervised use of Topical Corticosteroid, a preferred first line treatment of eczema, has increasingly been linked with undesirable skin effects, thus compromising the safety of the patient and therapy.

Objective: To examine the correlation between corticosteroid misuse and severity of skin changes, in order to highlight the risks and need for proper guidance in eczema management.

Methodology:

Selected clinical settings were used to conduct a descriptive cross sectional study during four months. The number of patients included were 37 with a non probability convenience sampling technique who were diagnosed with eczema. Data was gathered using questionnaire structured to sought the corticosteroid used, its potency, duration and associated skin changes.

Results:

There was a significant correlation between the use of corticosteroids pattern and the development of adverse cutaneous effects. The participants including females (72.97%) and males (27.03%) experienced Striae (10.8%), Skin thinning (8.1%), Hypertrichosis (10.8%) after >3 months use of Topical Corticosteroids. There was also a significant association between the use of steroids for a longer period and skin effects ($p = 0.006$) and frequency of application and adverse outcomes ($p = 0.000$). The results indicate the importance of careful use of corticosteroid, education of patients, and periodic clinical check-up.

Conclusion:

This study found that long-term and regular use of topical corticosteroids is strongly linked to negative effects on the skin such as striae, skin thinning, redness, and hypertrichosis in people with eczema.

It also lead to plan the eczema treatment according to severity index to reduce the potential side effects.

Introduction

Eczema is a skin disorder characterized by inflammation of the skin, with the subsequent severe dryness, itching, redness and swelling of the skin. It can also be a synonym for atopic dermatitis, and can occur all over the body. It tends to exacerbate when the skin barrier is destroyed, thereby predisposing the skin to the development of eczema-like alterations. Eczema or atopic dermatitis can happen at any age. (1)

The most used interventions are corticosteroids which are either topical or oral since they help in the reduction of inflammation. Other moisturizers and humectants can be combined with topical corticosteroids to restore normal skin barrier function. Drugs are used to help control eczema to decrease the number of flares and as immunosuppressive drugs. (2)

Steroids are sometimes used in excess or incorrectly, and this can lead to changes in the skin including atrophy, telangiectasia and even systemic changes. Corticosteroids may aid in the reconstruction of the skin barrier and the treatment of eczema, but it has certain boundaries on their application. Overuse can lead to skin deformities, including bleeding ulcers, undiagnosed infections, steroid dependency and bruises. (3)

Recent studies show that patients who use topical corticosteroids based on the guidelines do not have any signs of skin shrinkage, striae, or telangiectasia. Steroid dependence is another concern regarding the use of topical corticosteroids, where the skin becomes accustomed to the steroid and then abruptly stops taking them, and the eczema reemerges, usually with more severity than previously. This is usually experienced when applying strong steroids on sensitive areas such as the face, underarms, or genitals. Such dependency complicates the treatment or management of eczema greatly because individuals would apply topical corticosteroids blindly to obtain a temporary relief, which causes chronic pain. (4)(5)

The strength of the corticosteroid, the length, and the frequency of administration appear to influence the probability of TSWs, and thinner skin appears to be more likely to have it. A number of measures have been proposed to reduce risks yet achieve the therapeutic effect. The most significant aspect of AD management is emollient treatment. It assists in repair and maintenance of the skin barrier, reduces TEWL, and reduces the quantity and frequency of TCS required. (6)

It was also noted that long-term or regular use of topical corticosteroids, especially to face or genitals, may result in dependence and response to topical corticosteroids withdrawal. The manifestation of more serious skin changes indicates this condition as topical steroid withdrawal syndrome (TSWS). There is a lack of data and researches on the specific reaction and side effects of the treatment, with which additional researches in the local areas can provide more certain results in this direction. (7)

Some randomized trials and studies have been conducted on such cases of skin changes by the uses of topical corticosteroids; yet with their rising trends in local areas we require an extensive-research measures to document the number of individuals utilizing high or low-potency topical corticosteroids to treat eczema. The individuals why individuals who use topical corticosteroids in large amounts experience skin atrophy, striae, and telangiectasis. This is due to the fact that fibroblasts change, there is a reduction in the production of melanin and the feathers of the elastin and collagen are disorganized. (8)

Despite these advances, we still do not understand the frequency of TCS-related issues and how they change over time, particularly TSWS. Majority of the existing data are based on case reports, small series, or retrospective studies, but not on large-scale prospective studies. It is urgent that there should be a widespread epidemiological study using validated outcome measures to determine the level of use, to identify risk factors (e.g. potency, duration, anatomical location), and to

determine the effectiveness of educational interventions.

Methodology:

The study was designed as descriptive, cross-sectional study with non-probability sampling technique, done in supervised clinical settings. The sample size was kept 37 participants, with inclusion criteria of people with eczema, age 18-40 years both male and female should be using corticosteroids for more than 3 months with visible skin changes. The exclusion criteria include

people with Seborrheic Dermatitis, Fungal Infections or any related skin disorder, not using TCS for more than 3 months, with systemic corticosteroid use or with concurrent immunosuppressive disorders.

RESULTS

1. Demographic Characteristics of Participants:

The total number of participants in the study was 37. The mean age was 27.30 ± 6.66 years (range, 17-45 years) (Table 1, Figure 1).

Participant Age	
Mean	27.30
Std. Deviation	6.662
Minimum	17
Maximum	45

Table 1. Participant Age.

The table show that the age of the participants. The mean age of participant was 27.30 ± 6.66 years

old with Std.Deviation. The minimum age was 17 years and maximum age was 45 years.

Figure 1. Histogram of Participant Age.

Most of the participants were female (73%) with males accounting for 27%. Most of the patients were diagnosed with atopic dermatitis (67.6%) and eczema (21.6%) (Fig. 2).

Table 2. Participant Gender.

Table show that participant gender. The n=10(27.0%) was male participants, and n=27(73.0%) was female participants.

Participant Gender		
	Frequency	Percent
Male	10	27.0
Female	27	73.0
Total	37	100.0

Figure 2. Pie Chart of Participant Gender.

Table 3. Participant Diagnosis.

Table 3 show that participant diagnosis. The n=25(67.7%) have atopic dermatitis, n=8(21.6%) have eczema, and n=4(10.8%) have other.

Participant Diagnosis		
	Frequency	Percent
Eczema	25	67.6
Atopic Dermatitis	8	21.6
Other	4	10.8

Total	37	100.0
-------	----	-------

Table 4. Age at onset of eczema

Table show that the age at onset of eczema. The mean age was 9.49±6.22 years old with Std. Deviation. The minimum age was 0, and maximum age was 23 years old.

Age at onset of eczema	
Mean	9.49
Std. Deviation	6.221
Minimum	0
Maximum	23

The mean age of onset of eczema was 9.49 ± 6.22 years, suggesting early disease initiation from data from multiple centers.

Figure 4. Histogram of Age at onset of eczema

Table 5. Duration of current episode.

Table show that the duration of current episode. The n=1(2.7%) <1 month, n=16(43.2%) 1-3

months, n=15(40.5%) 3-12 months, and n=5(13.5%) >12 months.

Duration of current episode		
	Frequency	Percent
<1 month	1	2.7
1-3 months	16	43.2
3-12 months	15	40.5
>12 months	5	13.5
Total	37	100.0

Most of the participants reported a disease duration of 1-3 months (43.2%) or 3-12 months (40.5%), indicating chronic or recurrent patterns (Table 5).

Figure 5. Bar Chart of Duration of current episode.

Table 6. Usual affected areas.

Table show that the Usual affected areas. The n=4(10.8%) on face, n=3(8.1%) on scalp,

n=2(5.4%) on neck, n=1(2.7%) on trunk, n=2(5.4%) on arms, and so on show in table.

Usual affected areas (tick all that apply)		
	Frequency	Percent
Face	4	10.8
Scalp	3	8.1
Neck	2	5.4
Trunk	1	2.7
Arms	2	5.4
Hands	3	8.1
Legs	2	5.4
Feet	1	2.7
Genital	2	5.4
All of them	17	45.9
Total	37	100.0

Almost 45.9% of patients reported involvement of multiple body areas, indicating severe and widespread disease. (Table 6)

Figure 6. Bar Chart of Usual affected areas

2. Pattern of Corticosteroid Use:

Table 7. Type.

Table show that the type. The n=31(83.8%) Topical, n=4(10.8%) Oral, and n=2(5.4%) Inhaled.

Type	Frequency	Percent
Topical	31	83.8
Oral	4	10.8
Inhaled	2	5.4
Total	37	100.0

Topical was the most commonly used form of c 35 oids (83.8%), among other forms, including oral and inhaled that were the least taken options among the patients.

Figure 8. Bar Chart of Type.

Table 9. If topical – formulation.

Table show that the If topical – formulation. The n=19(51.4%) Cream, n=11(29.7%) Ointment, n=5(13.5%) Lotion, and n=2(5.4%) Gel.

If topical – formulation		
	Frequency	Percent
Cream	19	51.4
Ointment	11	29.7
Lotion	5	13.5
Gel	2	5.4
Total	37	100.0

Most preferred formulation was creams (51.4%) over other formulation like ointments, gels and sprays because of ease of application and availability in otc medications.

Figure 9. Bar Chart of If topical – formulation.

Table 10. Potency (if known).

Table show that the potency. The n=11(29.7%) have mild, n=11(29.7%) have moderate,

n=11(29.7%) have potent, n=3(8.1%) have very potent, and n=1(2.7%) have don't know.

Potency (if known)		
	Frequency	Percent
Mild	11	29.7
Moderate	11	29.7
Potent	11	29.7
Very potent	3	8.1
Don't know	1	2.7
Total	37	100.0

In terms of potency, an almost equal distribution was observed among mild, moderate and potent steroids (29.7% each) whereas 8.1% used very potent steroids.

Figure 10. Bar Chart of Potency (if known).

Table 11. Total duration of use (for this product). Table show that the Total duration of use (for this product). The n=3(8.1%) p<2 weeks, n=8(21.6%) 2-4 weeks, n=7(18.9%) 1-3 months, n=18(48.6%) >3 months, and n=1(2.7%) Intermittent/As needed.

Total duration of use (for this product)		
	Frequency	Percent
<2 weeks	3	8.1
2-4 weeks	8	21.6
1-3 months	7	18.9
>3 months	18	48.6
Intermittent/As needed	1	2.7
Total	37	100.0

Of concern was the fact that 48.6% of participants used corticosteroids for > 3 months and 67.5% had cumulative use > 3 months/year, indicating long-term exposure.

Figure 11. Bar Chart of Total duration of use (for this product).

Table 12. Frequency of application / dose.

Table show that the Frequency of application / dose. The n=15(40.5%) once daily, n=13(35.1%)

twice daily, n=2(5.4%) thrice daily, and n=7(18.9%) as needed.

Frequency of application / dose		
	Frequency	Percent
Once daily	15	40.5
Twice daily	13	35.1
Thrice daily	2	5.4
As needed	7	18.9
Total	37	100.0

Regarding frequency, most participants used steroids once per day (40.5%) or twice per day (35.1%), but some had usage beyond the recommendations

Figure 12. Bar Chart of Frequency of application / dose

Table 13. Adverse Effects Associated with Corticosteroid Use:
substantial portion of the participants reported side effects. The most common were: Striae (10,8%), Hypertrichosis (10.8 %),

Redness/burning (10.8%), Skin thinning (8.1%). Notably, 27% of participants reported multiple side effects, which indicates cumulative damage.

Have you experienced any side effects with topical corticosteroids? (tick all that apply)		
	Frequency	Percent
Skin thinning/atrophy	3	8.1
Stretch marks (striae)	4	10.8
Bruising	2	5.4
Increased hair growth (hypertrichosis)	4	10.8
Redness or burning	4	10.8
Worsening eczema (tachyphylaxis)	3	8.1
Contact dermatitis/irritation	2	5.4
Hypopigmentation/depigmentation	1	2.7
Perioral dermatitis	1	2.7
Acneiform eruptions	1	2.7
None	2	5.4
All of them	10	27.0
Total	37	100.0

Figure 14. Have you experienced any side effects with topical corticosteroids?

Table show that the Have you experienced any side effects with topical corticosteroids? result. The

n=3(8.1%) skin thinning/atrophy, n=4(10.8%) stretch marks (striae), n=2(5.4%) bruising, n=4(10.8%) increased hair growth

(hypertrichosis), n=4(10.8%) redness or burning, and so on.

Have you experienced any side effects with topical corticosteroids? (tick all that apply)

Have you experienced any side effects with topical corticosteroids? (tick al...

Figure 14. Bar Chart of Have you experienced any side effects with topical corticosteroids?

Table 15. Association Between Corticosteroid Use and Skin Changes:

The results demonstrate a clear relationship between: • Longer duration (>3 months) and increased side-effects. More severe skin changes

and higher potency steroids, More frequent/self-tuning and worsening outcomes. Additionally, 56.8% of participants were told to stop steroids because of side effects, further supporting the correlation between misuse and adverse outcomes

Have you ever been advised to stop steroid because of side effects?		
	Frequency	Percent
Yes	21	56.8
No	16	43.2
Total	37	100.0

Table 16. Have you ever been advised to stop steroid because of side effects?

Table show that the Have you ever been advised to stop steroid because of side effects? result. The n=21(56.8%) have yes, and n=16(43.2%) have no.

Figure 16. Bar Chart of Have you ever been advised to stop steroid because of side effects

Key Findings for duration of Corticosteroid use with skin effect:

The table show that pearson chi square result of p was 0.006 that is less than 0.05, its means that have

a significant result of duration of Corticosteroid use with Skin effect.

Table 17. Pearson Chi-Square (Duration of Corticosteroid use with Skin effect)

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	47.675 ^a	44	.006
Likelihood Ratio	45.132	44	.004
Linear-by-Linear Association	4.987	1	.026
N of Valid Cases	37		

a. 60 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .03.

The chi-square test shows a statistically significant association between the duration of corticosteroid use and occurrence of skin effects ($\chi^2 = 47.675$, $df = 44$, $p = 0.006$). This implies that the longer the

duration of corticosteroid use, the greater the probability and severity of adverse skin changes such as atrophy, striae and redness, demonstrating a clear association between prolonged use and skin

damage. This association was further supported by the likelihood ratio ($p = 0.004$) and suggested a trend toward worse effects with increasing duration by linear-by-linear association ($p = 0.026$). However, many cells had expected counts below 5 and therefore the findings should be interpreted cautiously although the overall association is meaningful.

Table 18. Pearson Chi-Square (Frequency of Corticosteroid use with Skin effect)

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	28.719 ^a	33	.000
Likelihood Ratio	28.301	33	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	.087	1	.009
N of Valid Cases	37		

a. 48 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .05.

The chi-square test shows a statistically significant association between the frequency of corticosteroid use and the occurrence of skin effects ($\chi^2 = 28.719$, $df = 33$, $p = 0.000$). The p-value was <0.05 , which indicates a significant association between more frequent application (e.g., several times per day) and increased risk of adverse skin changes such as irritation, atrophy, and redness. The likelihood ratio ($p = 0.000$) and the linear-by-linear association ($p = 0.009$) further support this strong association and the tendency for the skin effects to worsen with increasing frequency. Nevertheless, the results should be interpreted with caution although the findings were significant, as many cells had expected counts less than 5.

DISCUSSION

The current cross-sectional study was done to investigate the association between the growing usage of topical corticosteroids and the accompanying skin alterations in the patients of eczema. The study results showed a statistically significant correlation between lengthy duration and higher frequency of corticosteroid use and unfavorable skin effects. These findings support the concept that corticosteroids misuse and overuse are important factors leading to dermatological problems in eczema patients.

Key Findings for duration of Corticosteroid use with skin effect:

The table show that pearson chi square result of p was 0.006 that is less than 0.05, its means that have a significant result of frequency of Corticosteroid use with Skin effect.

The demographic results of the study revealed that most of the participants were females (73%) with a mean age of 27.30 ± 6.66 years. Christensen et al. (2024) showed similar results with a higher prevalence of chronic eczema in women, which was attributed to higher healthcare-seeking behaviors and more exposure to cosmetic and environmental factors. (10) In the present study, the mean age of beginning was 9.49 ± 6.22 years. This indicates that eczema often develops in childhood. This is consistent with the findings of Schmitt et al. (2011) who showed that atopic dermatitis is usually present in early development and often persists into maturity as a chronic recurrent disorder.

In the present study, 48.6% of patients used corticosteroids consistently for more than three months, and 67.5% had a cumulative exposure of more than three months per year. These data suggest a large population of people with eczema who are dependent on corticosteroids for long periods of time. Barta et al. (2023) found similar findings, noting that almost half of eczema patients used corticosteroids long-term and experienced increasing symptoms with prolonged exposure. (5) Similarly, Bilal et al. (2023) highlighted the fact that the long-term use of corticosteroids without sufficient medical care often leads to steroid misuse, dependence, and various severe cutaneous reactions. (6) In terms of

the frequency of application, the majority of the participants in the present study applied corticosteroids once (40.5%) or twice (35.1%) day, while a smaller number of them applied corticosteroids more frequently than indicated. Administration once a day has been observed to have almost the same therapeutic efficacy as numerous administrations per day with less side effects and better patient compliance (Green et al., 2005). (26)

Brunner et al. (2016) and Eichenfield et al. (2014) also found that results were not improved by application frequency above twice daily, and there may be an increased risk of skin injury. The present findings consequently suggest that the increased application frequency in some participants may have unnecessarily led to unfavorable effects without additional therapeutic benefit. (7)(20)

The study showed that mild, moderate and potent corticosteroids were administered almost equally in terms of corticosteroid potency but a lesser fraction of highly potent steroids was used. Kulthanan et al. (2021) said that high potency corticosteroids should be used only for severe disease and thicker skin areas, as incorrect usage on sensitive areas such as the face, groin, and axilla might cause substantial difficulties. Guttman-Yassky et al. (2025) also emphasized that low-potency corticosteroids are safer than high-potency corticosteroids for long-term therapy, especially youngsters and in areas with thin skin. The use of powerful steroids by participants in the current study may possibly explain the higher incidence of sequelae such as atrophy, erythema, and striae. (27)

The most prevalent adverse effects described in the present study were striae, hypertrichosis, redness or burning feelings and skin thinning. Moreover, 27% of the subjects had simultaneous numerous unfavorable symptoms suggestive of cumulative steroid harm. These findings are highly correlated to Egeberg et al. (2024) who observed skin atrophy, burning, fissures, and exacerbation of eczema symptoms among chronic corticosteroid users. (21) Feldman et al. (2007) have reported that continuous use of topical corticosteroids can lead to telangiectasia, hypopigmentation, acneiform

eruptions, purpura and steroid-induced rosacea. Similarly, corticosteroids have been found to disrupt collagen synthesis and epidermal turnover, resulting in skin thinning and fragility (Siegfried et al., 2016). Thus, the present study provides more evidence for the association of chronic corticosteroid exposure with structural skin damage. (23)

The current investigation also revealed a statistically significant connection between corticosteroid duration with skin effects ($p = 0.006$). The severity of atrophy, striae and redness increased with greater exposure duration. These findings are reinforced by Axon et al. (2022) who noted that extended corticosteroid therapy has a higher risk of rebound dermatitis and topical steroid withdrawal syndrome. Yu et al. (2018) further elaborated that persistent exposure to corticosteroids causes tachyphylaxis, whereby the skin gradually becomes less sensitive to the treatment, prompting patients to increase the dose and frequency of treatment, thus aggravating bad consequences. (4)

Another notable finding of the present study was that 56.8% of participants had previously been recommended to stop the usage of steroids due to negative effects. This is indicative of the growing worry over the topical steroid withdrawal syndrome (TSWS). TSWS was described by Hoe et al. (2025) and Sjobeck et al. (2024) as a potential complication of long-term and short-term corticosteroid treatment and can manifest with erythema, burning, desquamation, and severe rebound inflammation.

Likewise, Reich et al. (2022) reported that TSWS is commonly misinterpreted as worsening eczema, resulting in many steroid prescriptions and delayed healing. Thus, the outcomes of this study highlight the significance of increased awareness and early detection of steroid withdrawal problems. (29)

Topical formulations, especially creams, were the most commonly utilized corticosteroid preparations, according to the study. Formulation type was shown to affect corticosteroid potency and side-effect profile, with ointments generally more effective than creams due to increased absorption (Silverberg et al., 2024). This preference

for creams among the participants may be because of the ease of application and the availability of these products over the counter. However, the overuse and problems of corticosteroids remain major contributors to self-medication and unsupervised access. (28)

The clinical implications of this investigation are pertinent. Corticosteroids are still the gold standard of treatment for eczema, due to their potent anti-inflammatory properties, but incorrect and chronic use can result in considerable compromise in skin integrity and patient quality of life. The study underscores the need for patient counseling, optimal potency selection, restricted therapy duration, and regular dermatological monitoring. Clinicians should promote the lowest effective potency and consider steroid-sparing agents, moisturisers and non-steroidal therapy if possible.

However, there are certain limitations of the study despite the notable findings. The relatively small sample size and use of convenience sampling may restrict generalizability of results to the larger population. In addition, many of the cells in the chi-square tables had anticipated counts less than five which indicates that care should be taken in interpreting statistical relationships. Future studies should include larger multicenter populations and longitudinal follow-up to further investigate corticosteroid safety profiles and long-term results.

Overall, the findings of the current study are in line with the previously published literature. The findings strongly support the conclusion that greater duration and frequency of the use of corticosteroid are significantly associated with unfavorable skin changes among eczema patients. The study highlights the critical need for evidence-based prescribing, patient education and better long-term care techniques for eczema.

Limitations

- The study was done in limited clinical settings, which may not be representative of other regions
- Lack of long-term follow-up limits understanding of chronic effects and progression

- Small sample size limits generalisability of findings to a larger population

Recommendations

- There is a need to emphasize more patient education on the right use of corticosteroids, notably on potency selection, limited duration, and optimal frequency of application.
- Advising patients to use low potency corticosteroids on regular or sensitive regions and not for prolonged or unsupervised application greatly minimizes the probability of undesirable skin changes.
- Once daily administration during active flare-ups should be recommended as increasing the frequency does not improve the therapeutic outcomes but increases the problems.
- Preventative interventions should include the function of emollients and moisturisers as first-line and maintenance therapy to restore the skin barrier and limit dependence on corticosteroids.
- From a policy aspect, there is a need for stricter control of the over-the-counter availability of strong corticosteroids to decrease the potential for misuse.

CONCLUSION

The present study was undertaken to evaluate the link of growing trend of corticosteroid use and its related skin alterations among eczema patients. Results: The length and frequency of corticosteroid treatment were statistically significantly associated with the development of unfavorable dermatological effects. The mean age of the 37 participants was 27.30 ± 6.66 years and 73 % were females. The majority of the subjects had a diagnosis of eczema (67.6%) and atopic dermatitis (21.6%). The mean age of starting was 9.49 ± 6.22 years, which indicates that the condition started early.

The data showed that the most often used medication was topical corticosteroids (83.8%) and the preferred formulation was creams (51.4%). usage of light, moderate and high corticosteroids was about similar (29.7% each) while 8.1% reported usage of very potent steroids. Of particular concern is the fact that 48.6% of subjects had a history of corticosteroid usage for

>3 months and 67.5% reported a cumulative duration of yearly use of >3 months, which is a worrying trend for long-term exposure.

The study found several detrimental effects of corticosteroids misuse. The most prevalent side effects were striae (10.8%), hypertrichosis (10.8%), redness or burning feelings (10.8%) and skin thinning/atrophy (8.1%). Additionally, 27% of participants reported the occurrence of more than one side effect at the same time, suggesting cumulative skin damage associated to long-term corticosteroid treatment. Moreover, 56.8% of individuals had been previously recommended to quit steroid therapy because of adverse effects, indicating rising clinician knowledge of corticosteroid-related problems.

Statistical study confirmed the substantial correlation between corticosteroid duration and skin effects. The chi-square test with a Pearson Chi-Square value of 47.675, degrees of freedom (df) = 44 and $p = 0.006$ demonstrated a statistically significant connection between length of corticosteroid treatment and unfavorable skin changes. The likelihood ratio was similarly significant ($p = 0.004$) and the linear-by-linear association showed a pattern of gradual worsening with increasing length ($p = 0.026$). Similarly, the

frequency of corticosteroid use demonstrated a significantly significant association with skin damage with Pearson Chi-Square = 28.719, $df = 33$ and $p = 0.000$. The likelihood ratio was significant ($p = 0.000$) and the linear-by-linear association indicated a worsening effect with increasing frequency of application ($p = 0.009$).

The data provide compelling evidence that long-term use, greater frequency and improper potency selection of corticosteroids are major contributors to unfavorable skin outcomes in eczema. The study underlines the need of careful prescription, patient counselling, consistent follow up and use of least effective potency for the minimum time. It is important to educate on safe use of corticosteroids, particularly on approaches to slow tapering, to avoid consequences such as skin atrophy, tachyphylaxis, and topical steroid withdrawal syndrome.

In conclusion, while topical corticosteroids remain quite useful for managing eczema, the overuse of these medications poses a considerable threat to the health of the skin. Evidence-based prescribing methods, more patient knowledge and safer long-term care options are required to decrease corticosteroid-related problems and enhance patient outcomes.

Cases

Figure 1.1

Figure 1.1 is a 24 years old female with eczema suffering from redness and hyperpigmentation due to frequent use of betamethasone twice daily for more than 6 months without an emollient.

Figure 1.2

Figure 1.2 shows a 19 years old female with mild bruising, skin atrophy and dryness due to excessive use of different topical corticosteroids frequently to control eczema.

Figure 1.3

Figure 1.3 shows a 31 years old male suffering from eczema for a long time and was using topical corticosteroids for management and treatment without any prescription or supervision. He is facing severe hyperpigmentation, bruising and eczema flares and rebounding due to excessive and uncontrolled use.

Figure 1.4

Figure 1.4 shows a 44 years old female with severe skin changes due to use of topical corticosteroids for past years to control eczema. She has been using the drugs on and off making the skin addicted leading to telangiectasia, skin thinning, striae and hyperpigmentation due to excessive use.

Figure 1.5

Figure 1.5 shows a 26 years old female suffering from Hypertrichosis induced due to use of topical corticosteroids to control eczematous condition of face. She has been dealing with eczema since childhood and was using different topical corticosteroids at least thrice daily without any prescription and medical supervision.

REFERENCES

- Ainley-Walker PF, Patel L, David TJ. Side-to-side comparison of topical treatment in atopic dermatitis. *Arch Dis Child.* 1998;79:149-152.
- Andersen YM, Egeberg A, Ban L, et al. Association between topical corticosteroid use and type 2 diabetes in two European population-based adult cohorts. *Diabetes Care.* 2019;42(6):1095-1103.
- Arellano FM, Wentworth CE, Arana A, Fernández C, Paul CF. Risk of lymphoma following exposure to calcineurin inhibitors and topical steroids in patients with atopic dermatitis. *J Invest Dermatol.* 2007;127(4):808-816.
- Axon E, Howells L, Santer M, et al. Strategies for using topical corticosteroids in children and adults with eczema. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev.* 2022;3:CD013090.
- Barta K, et al. Corticosteroid exposure and cumulative effects in patients with eczema: results from a patient survey. *Ann Allergy Asthma Immunol.* 2023;130(1):93-99.e10.
- Bilal H, Showkat M, Tabassum N. Eczema, etiology and treatment. In: *Natural Products for Treatment of Skin and Soft Tissue Disorders.* Bentham Science Publishers; 2023. p. 1-49.
- Brunner PM, et al. A mild topical steroid leads to progressive anti-inflammatory effects in the skin of patients with moderate-to-severe atopic dermatitis. *J Allergy Clin Immunol.* 2016.

- Burr S. Emollients for managing dry skin conditions. *Prof Nurse*. 1999;15(1):43-48.
- Chen Q, et al. Short-term efficacy and safety of biologics and Janus kinase inhibitors for patients with atopic dermatitis: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Heliyon*. 2023.
- Choi JY, Dawe R, Ibbotson S, et al. Quantitative analysis of topical treatments in atopic dermatitis. *Br J Dermatol*. 2020;182(4):1017-1025.
- Chong M, Fonacier L. Treatment of eczema: corticosteroids and beyond. *Clin Rev Allergy Immunol*. 2016;51(3):249-262.
- Chu AWL, et al. Systemic treatments for atopic dermatitis (eczema): systematic review and network meta-analysis of randomized trials. *J Allergy Clin Immunol*. 2023.
- Dabade TS, Davis DMR, Wetter DA, et al. Wet dressing therapy in severe pediatric atopic dermatitis. *J Am Acad Dermatol*. 2012.
- Davis DMR, et al. Guidelines of care for atopic dermatitis in adults. *J Am Acad Dermatol*. 2024.
- DCTN UK. Eczema treatment research priorities. Nottingham: UK Dermatology Clinical Trials Network; 2012.
- Diehl KL, Cohen PR. Topical steroid-induced perioral dermatitis. *Cureus*. 2021;13(4):e14443.
- Drucker A, et al. International Eczema Council consensus on systemic corticosteroids. *Br J Dermatol*. 2018;178(3):768-775.
- Eckert L, Gupta S, Amand C, et al. Impact of atopic dermatitis on quality of life. *J Am Acad Dermatol*. 2017;77(2):274-279.
- Egeberg A, Schlapbach C, Haugaard JH, et al. Adverse events from topical corticosteroids in hand eczema. *JAAD Int*. 2024;14:77-83.
- El-Heis S, Crozier SR, Healy E, et al. Prenatal growth and atopic eczema. *Clin Epidemiol*. 2018;10:1851-1864.
- Feldman SR, Camacho FT, Krejci-Manwaring J, et al. Adherence to topical therapy and office visits. *J Am Acad Dermatol*. 2007;57(1):81-83.
- Gao Q, et al. Abrocitinib and upadacitinib vs dupilumab. *Heliyon*. 2023.
- Gradwell C, McGarvey S. Dry skin condition care. *Dermatol Nurs*. 2006;5(2):8-10.
- Green C, Colquitt J, Kirby J, Davidson P. Once-daily vs frequent topical corticosteroids. *Br J Dermatol*. 2005;152(1):130-141.
- Guttman-Yassky E, et al. Atopic dermatitis. *Lancet*. 2025.
- Hajar T, Leshem YA, Hanifin JM, et al. Topical corticosteroid withdrawal review. *J Am Acad Dermatol*. 2015;72(3):541-549.
- Schmitt J, et al. Eczema clinical evidence. *BMJ Clin Evid*. 2011.
- Silverberg JI, et al. Tapinarof phase 3 trials. *J Am Acad Dermatol*. 2024.
- Reich K, et al. Abrocitinib vs dupilumab. *Lancet*. 2022.